

DiSSCo Transition Project

Machine Annotation Service Hackathon

Work Package 3

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Executive Summary

The first Machine Annotation Service (MAS) Hackathon organised by Work Package 3 (WP3), took place at the Senckenberg Research Institute in Frankfurt from March 24th to March 26th, 2025. The event was conducted in a hybrid format allowing both online and in-person participation, and the hackathon was open to all DiSSCo stakeholders. A total of 15 participants from 10 different organisations took part in the hackathon.

The event began with an introduction to the concept of Machine Annotation Services and a walkthrough on how to develop them within the DiSSCo infrastructure. Additionally, discussions were held around the MAS policy framework and the general structure of a Service Level Agreement (SLA) for MAS deployments.

Following the introductory sessions, participants formed three groups each focusing on a distinct use case. By the end of the hackathon, all three use cases were successfully implemented and deployed as Machine Annotation Services within the DiSSCo infrastructure.

Keywords

DiSSCO, Machine Annotation Service, Biohackathon, Machine learning, Large language models, ontoGPT

List of abbreviations

CA - Consortium Agreement

D - Deliverable

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

GA - Grant Agreement

MS - Milestone

RFC - Request For Comments

RI - Research Infrastructure

WP - Work Package

MAS - Machine Annotation Service

1. Introduction

In the DiSSCO Transition project as part of work package 3, the Machine Learning Assisted Plant Organ Segmentation (MAS) service was developed and integrated into the DiSSCO infrastructure (MS16: *Pilot integration of Machine Learning-assisted services for data enrichment with DSarch to create a coherent framework enabling seamless integration of machine-annotated data with the Digital Specimens*). Using this MAS as a reference model, the hackathon aimed to bring more Machine Annotated Service into the DiSSCO infrastructure. Having this as the motive, the first MAS Hackathon was organised. In preparation for the hackathon participants' datasets were ingested into the DiSSCO infrastructure to support their use cases. Additionally, reference content based on the existing MAS use case was created along with comprehensive documentation and presentations to introduce the concept of Machine Annotation Services [1].

The hackathon was delivered in a hybrid format to 15 participants at the Senckenberg Research Institute in Frankfurt running from March 24th to March 26th, 2025 (noon to noon).

During the event, participants developed three Machine Annotation Services:

- **Machine Annotation Service for extracting structured information using OntoGPT**
- **Taxamorph Machine Annotation Service**
- **Plant Trait Detection Machine Annotation Service**

2. Hackathon Objectives

The hackathon had the following objectives:

- 1) Gain a understanding of what a Machine Annotation Service (MAS) is and how it can be integrated into the DiSSCO infrastructure;
- 2) Become familiar with Machine Annotation Service and DiSSCover platform;
- 3) Learn how to develop Machine Annotation Services tailored to the individual use cases;
- 4) Develop the Machine Annotation Service wrappers for their own case;
- 5) Integrate the Machine Annotation Service into the DiSSCO infrastructure;
- 6) Assess practices and safeguards required for Machine Annotation Services in DiSSCO to support the implementation of DiSSCO's MAS Policy [2].

3. Hackathon Preparation

The Machine Annotation Service (MAS) can be scheduled on the data integrated in the DiSSCover platform. To support MAS use cases effectively, relevant datasets must be ingested into the DiSSCover system. Currently, DiSSCo enables data ingestion through designated endpoints. Prior to the hackathon, participants are contacted to collect datasets which are then ingested into the platform.

A handout is prepared and distributed to participants and a GitHub repository is created for code submissions [3]. Additionally, a Slack channel is established to facilitate communication among participants and a Zoom link is shared for those attending online.

Comprehensive developer documentation for the Machine Annotation Service was created by the DiSSCo hub team. A presentation is also prepared to provide participants with a detailed introduction to the design and development of MAS.

4. Hackathon Agenda

The three-day noon to noon hackathon included the following activities:

Day 1: Introduction to the event, MAS concept and policy overview and a live demo of the annotation and model development tool by Laurens Hogeweg (Naturalis).

Day 2: Hands-on development of Machine Annotation Services including endpoint setup MAS wrapper integration. Teams received ongoing support and participated in group discussions. The day concluded with a social dinner.

Day 3: Teams finalised their work and prepared the presentations and showcased their results. The event ended with short feedback and a closing session.

5. Hackathon Delivery

During the hackathon the participants worked on three teams where each team focused on creating Machine Annotation Service (MAS) for their specific use case.

Each team either had their own external endpoint or developed a new one during the hackathon. These endpoints will process the digital media or digital specimen from the DiSSCover platform and the results are wrapped by MAS according to openDS specification.

Team 1: OntoGPT – Habitat Information Extraction

This team developed a MAS based on OntoGPT focused on extracting structured habitat-related information from unstructured text using LLM techniques.

The Key steps are:

- Setting up a custom external endpoint powered by OntoGPT;
- Extracting entities and relationships relevant to habitat descriptors;
- Mapping extracted data into the DiSSCo data model using the openDS schema;
- Implementing the MAS wrapper for integration with the DiSSCover platform.

Team 2: Taxamorph – Specimen Image Classification

The Taxamorph team developed a service that leverages AI based image classification to assign taxonomic labels (family, genus, species) to specimen images.

Their system included:

- An external service endpoint for performing specimen image classification;
- The results are mapped to openDS schema and implemented the MAS wrapper for integration with the DiSSCover platform.

Team 3: Plant Trait Detection Machine Annotation Service

This team focused on identifying and extracting plant traits from digital herbarium specimens. Their MAS included:

- An external service endpoint for plant organ detection using leaf machine;
- The results are mapped to openDS schema and implemented with the MAS wrapper for integration with the DiSSCover platform.

6. Outcomes, Results, Challenges

All teams successfully developed their Machine Annotation Services (MAS) and integrated them with the DiSSCo platform. The event concluded with team presentations where participants showcased their approaches and results.

Some challenges included onboarding participants without a development background particularly in setting up and working with tools like OntoGPT—as well

as ensuring smooth coordination with online participants throughout the event.

A feedback form was shared with all participants and responses will be collected to evaluate the event and to identify areas for improvement. Overall, the hackathon was a productive and successful collaboration resulting in functional MAS implementations and valuable cross-disciplinary engagement.

7. Future Work

Future work includes organising the MAS Hackathon as an annual event to engage a wider range of participants, foster collaboration and support the continued development and integration of MAS within the DiSSCo infrastructure.

8. References

[1] MAS Developer Documentation.

<https://discco.github.io/mas-developers-documentation/>

[2] MAS Policy (Draft Version 0.2):

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1kCBqhhWS1mJqs765JjoYKuH2CdaaH0Zna-giS5h_Emw/edit?tab=t.0

[3] Github repository <https://github.com/DiSSCo/demo-enrichment-service-image/>